

TEACHING ENGLISH TO STUDENTS THROUGH INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Annotation. This article provides teaching English to students by using interactive methods as well as ways to use multiple techniques during the lesson.

Аннотация. В этой статье рассказывается о преподавании английского языка студентом с использованием интерактивных методов, а также о способах использования различных техник во время урока.

Key words: teaching, interactive, game, create, role playing, process, method.

The term “interactive English” is also used by physical institutes to refer to a learning style that involves discussion, role play, and frequent interaction with the instructor. In a typical language school, many learning methods are based on passive activities such as listening and reading. While these activities are necessary for any student wishing to learn English grammar and vocabulary, they should be complemented with others to facilitate the acquisition of communication skills. Interactive English learning techniques help develop these communication skills by demanding a response from the student, whether participating in discussions with other students, interacting with the teacher, or working with audio-visual teaching devices. Interactive learning methods are based on the theory that the reproduction of speech for the purpose of direct communication accelerates the assimilation of grammar and vocabulary.

Interactive learning is a pedagogical approach that integrates social media and urban computing into ethical design and delivery. Interactive learning has emerged in particular with the significant increase in students' use of digital technology and virtual

communication. After about 2000, students entering higher education institutions expect interactive learning to become an integral part of their education.

Interactive learning is any form of academic or academic curriculum that uses computer technology to emphasize or teach specific material. Online lectures and virtual classrooms are examples of highly interactive learning, but when computers enter the learning space as learning games or structured inquiry tools, the resulting lessons can be considered interactive. In some groups, hands-on learning is considered interactive. While this app is great, it is generally considered outdated. When modern scientists talk about classroom interaction, they almost always talk about technology and often the Internet. Interactive learning is generally considered the opposite of passive observational learning. Students usually need a combination of passive and active learning to master concepts. If everything is interactive, students run the risk of getting too excited or missing the main objective. However, when learning is completely passive, students can lose interest and focus. Teachers typically try to balance incorporating passive learning methods and techniques, such as lectures and independent study, with active assignments that allow students to experience instruction in new and often unexpected environments. The two systems work best against each other. Classroom games allow students to learn while competing. These games can take many forms and can be applied to almost any subject. Incorporating games into the classroom has clear benefits. Breaking away from the traditional teaching and learning methods of the past decades, teachers can introduce highly engaging interactive games to their students. student participation

Lectures and individual activities have been widely used in classrooms for centuries, but these tools are not the most effective means of motivating students. Games are often much more effective in encouraging student engagement. Players have an intrinsic motivation to win. This drive keeps people engaged and learning along the way. Games also allow students to interact with the material in a hands-on way rather than requiring them to search and retain information. promotes teamwork

Some games are solitaire activities, but most require teamwork. Students need teamwork as soon as they leave school and enter the real world. Teamwork is beneficial in many situations. By having students participate in the game, teachers allow students to practice working together. To work effectively in groups, students must respect their peers and collaborate with them to reach a conclusion or solve a problem. In the real world, we often have to work with people we don't like, like in classroom games, we don't work with our best friends. Develop good sportsmanship

Sportsmanship is the ability to respond gracefully to win and lose situations. People who show good sportsmanship do not get upset when they lose, nor do they show outward signs of anger when they lose. They may still fear their loss, but they can channel that emotion into preparing for the upcoming game. Likewise, winners are not too proud or arrogant. They can celebrate a victory, but not at the expense of their opponents. As students play during practice, they develop the skills they need to become better players. Managing win-loss in this complex way takes practice, and these academic games give students the experience they need to respond appropriately to any outcome. Practice your problem solving skills.

The most popular methods are role-playing, brainstorming, case study method, presentations and discussions. They develop communication skills, logical thinking and various types of intellectual activity such as analysis, synthesis, comparison and generalization. These student-centred methods are very suitable, especially to more actively involve students in the acquisition of knowledge, skills and strategies.

It is known that role-playing determines the learning process in the university more educational and qualified, improving interdisciplinary relationships, connecting with the theory with the real needs of the professional sector and develop the necessary skills for future specialists. The most important element is the role-playing game that provides the opportunity to do this skills that are difficult to acquire under normal learning conditions. A role-playing game can take place in two ways: scripted and unscripted. With a role play scenario, teacher can use an example from a textbook. It's a good idea for a warm-up, have

everyone break into pairs and allow them to do so talk to their partner and play different roles. Unscripted ones are such RPGs when students are assigned certain roles and must use all their knowledge to talk to partners.

After mentioned the specified methods, we can conclude interactive teaching methods contribute to the optimization of the learning process during the study English. They intend to set up motivation mechanisms and increase them efficiency of teaching English communication. Use advantages interactive methods in the student's learning process include the maximum approach to the real conditions of professional activity, the broad autonomy of students, decision - taken under conditions of creative competition and development skills for spontaneous language, promoting the development of organizational skills students, the barrier between studying the language and its practical overcoming application.

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